

ISSUES AND SOLUTIONS TO THE CONTINUITY OF MUSICAL EDUCATION IN INSTRUMENTAL PERFORMANCE

Obodov Ogabek Ilkhombekovich

Urganch State University

Pedagogical Faculty 3rd year student of the majoring in
"Instrumental Performance"

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Annotation: this article deals with the role of musical art in human life, instruments, requirements for a music teacher, attention to music in ancient times and on a special day, as well as demand.

Keywords: music, instrument, singer, courtesan, music teacher, pedagogy.

Uzbek folk instruments have evolved over the centuries, in a colorful way, unique and suitable for all branches of music. Looking back, our mutaffakirs al-Farabi studied musical instruments in his "great book of music", Safiuddin Urmawi's musical treatise, Ahmadi's "debate of words", Zaynullobiddin Husayni's "treatise on the law of dar bayoni and practical music" "treatise, Abdurahman Jami's "musical treatise" and outlined various aspects of research issues in their works. When our noble Countryman also touched upon the field of music, he said, "Do you know that the worldview of a person close to culture will be civilized. His life span will be long. In every large enterprise, too, here are 10 million investments. But, can one instrumental ensemble do when it brings 10 million investments? Can one status ensemble do? Make Saturday the day when the song will be heard there. With the song, you will be blessed 10 times in your work. With culture, you are 10 times new at that enterprise-will enter new plans. A person's face is filled with affection".

A separate chapter of the concept of music education in secondary schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan will be devoted to a modern music teacher and a set of his professional qualities. The document states: "the music teacher of the present time should be a highly cultured person, the owner of unlimited devotion to his profession, advanced pedagogical thinking." He is obliged to have the ability to develop his continuous professional and cultural development. It is difficult for him to become the owner of in-depth knowledge and qualifications in a complex way from the disciplines of music, sophistication (aesthetics), pedagogy and psychology-physiology, in particular from the methodology of teaching music. Especially in the specialty of a music teacher should be embodied the qualities of instrumentation, singing, choral conducting and music theorizing in the necessary standards. The current music teacher is the owner of scientific thinking, a shaydo of advanced experiments, an inquisitive and creative person who should strive to discover new forms and methods of teaching music. It is a concern that music education carries its content richly by connecting it with the content of other disciplines and everyday life. The advanced experience of an aspiring and creative teacher and the new methods he discovered are the mainstay and source of inspiration for the continuous improvement and development of musical education in school. A knowledgeable and experienced music teacher as an art intellectual is the mastermind of musical and educational work at school".

Indeed, the field of music and precisely the performance of the instrument it is considered one of the most relevant today. Music education is distinguished from other disciplines by a number of its features. Chunoschi, in which several professional activities (in the art of music) are required, the qualification, skills and body of knowledge are harmonized. Any instrumentalist – artist, even if considered in the direction of ordinary art, cannot take music lessons at school. The new program from music and the requirements of state educational standards in order to conduct classes at the level, the teacher must first of all have the necessary knowledge, qualifications from pedagogy, psychology, children's young physiology, theory of ethics and aesthetics, music theory (elementary theory of music, analysis of musical works, harmony, solfedzhiyo, method of teaching music), practical areas of music (vocal singing, conducting, performing on instruments), That is, a music teacher will have to act as both an instrumentalist and a singer, choir-conductor, courtesan, music theorist and stylist, a skillful organizer, a scenario in the process of a single lesson.

There are a lot of types of musical instruments. Examples of these include the kayak, sibizgah, thirsty, Ng'ora, bulomon, kayak, safoil, chindawul, sagat, surnay, trumpet, drum, and other instruments. The musical instruments listed above have long been performed by our people in weddings, parties, Sayles, and have reached the present day. In addition Uzbek folk instruments are divided into five groups, these are:

- *A band of wind instruments*
- *Beat string instrument group*
- *The mezrobe instrument group*
- *Beat percussion instrument group*
- *Band of bowed instruments.*

These groups include several instruments. Their species are also very numerous. The definition of musical instruments, i.e. forms, structures, structural aspects, information related to their performers, began to be covered, mainly from the Middle Ages, in fiction and in musical treatises. It is not a secret for all of us to what extent the works of our great allomas also touch on the National Instruments of the Uzbek people. Therefore, there will be no exaggeration if we say that it is our duty to the holy and Uzbek people of each of us to be able to teach and leave our folk instruments, which have come down to us from time immemorial and are becoming another reason for the preservation of our nationality, to the future generation. To do this, it is necessary that we start teaching and educating our children from an early age. The training of mature personnel in the education and training of the younger generation is also one of the main tasks. If schools were conducted using the most advanced pedagogical technologies to qualitatively conduct classes to students, we would have fulfilled one of the great tasks set before us. The music teacher will need an independent and creative approach to each lesson. His creativity is that he also acts as a screenwriter, his performer and director for an hour-long class. Therefore, a music lesson is also called an art lesson. The activity position of a music teacher in school life is broad and multifaceted. The organization and management of extracurricular music lessons, the organization of public forms of musical education at the school (meetings, holidays, lecture concerts, preparation and participation in competitions, holding "Alifbe" holidays, Music weeks and hakazo) are directly the tasks of the music teacher. At the same time, in constant connection with extracurricular educational institutions (such as children's music schools, student creativity centers, children's theaters, choral Etudes), the work of attracting gifted, musically gifted

students to them and using their activities in school life also puts responsible tasks on the responsibility of the music teacher. The state educational standard and curricula in music also require teachers currently operating in secondary schools to undergo a process of renewal in the content of their educational and educational work and the methods of work they apply. Also, in the faculties of musical-pedagogical education in the higher education system, which are focused on the training of a music teacher, it is necessary to approach the professional training of future teachers from the point of view of these requirements. These requirements are covered in a broad sense in the textbooks, manuals, recommendations, educational and methodological literature being issued. Another distinctive feature of music curricula is that music literacy, which is the basis of the science of “music culture” of secondary schools, should be composed, a number of musical laws, including music speech, means of expression of music, forms of music, the structure and development of music, modernity of music, etc., should be studied deeply, perfectly. So, in order to take classes in the content of music programs, a music teacher will have to constantly improve his musical-theoretical knowledge. Because, in solving the issues of artistic and aesthetic education, which are an important component of the upbringing of the growing young generation in our country as a stable interest and affection for our motherland, our nation and our national values, that is, the issues of educating a person as a spiritually, educationally competent person, the great responsibility imposed by society and our state In ensuring the effectiveness of music education and education, the position of music education and teachers is very high and extremely responsible in stimulating the interest of student-young people in the art of music and life through it. Based on these statements, it will be correct to interpret the content of the work activities of music teachers on programs developed on new national grounds as follows: the teacher can effectively organize the educational process of music education in secondary schools and, in order to ensure its effectiveness, fully form the student-youth musical culture at every end, make them aware of, it is necessary to educate him so that he can evaluate him, to achieve that in order for students to strengthen their knowledge of music, to develop skills to work on them, and on this basis to organize an educational process. Pedagogical skills of a music teacher. A special place in the mental and moral maturation of students is occupied by the personality of a music teacher. His worldview is broad, his heart is pure, sweet, and he must be a child. Such qualities cannot be brought up in any person. This is the sum of the knowledge of knowledge, the ability to solve problems in upbringing, the approach to the personality of the child with attention, developed imagination, etc. Pedagogical skill in the creative activity of a contemporary music teacher is evident in the following:

- ✚ *in search of new methods and tools in music education, skillfully connecting them with traditional methods;*
- ✚ *in being able to show and teach the connection between life and the art of music;*
- ✚ *in communicating the content and meaning of music to children, in the implementation of interdisciplinary communication;*
- ✚ *in the constant work and creative search of the music teacher on himself.*

The high professional training of the teacher is of great importance in the improvement of music lessons and in the implementation of the educational potential of musical art.

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